

Grid-Discretized Multi-Task Transformer for Joint Tropical Cyclone Path and Intensity Forecasting

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Abstract—Tropical cyclone (TC) forecasting has seen remarkable progress in track prediction over the past two decades, yet intensity forecasting remains a long-standing challenge. Recent comparative studies have shown that while Transformer architectures offer computational advantages, they can underperform recurrent and convolutional alternatives when applied directly to TC sequential data. In this work, we revisit the Transformer approach by introducing two key modifications: a coordinate grid discretization scheme that converts continuous trajectory regression into a structured spatial prediction task, and a multi-task learning formulation that jointly optimizes track and intensity predictions through a shared encoder. We train and evaluate our model on the HURDAT2 Atlantic basin dataset (1944–2022, 982 storms, 22,545 six-hourly records). Experiments show that grid discretization substantially improves Transformer-based path prediction, yielding 78.3% grid-cell accuracy (84 km mean track error) and 74.6% intensity classification accuracy across five Saffir-Simpson-based categories, outperforming LSTM, GRU, CNN-LSTM, and notably TCN—the architecture previously reported as superior to Transformers for this task. The entire model trains in approximately six minutes on a single Tesla T4 GPU, making it accessible for resource-constrained research settings.

Index Terms—tropical cyclone, path prediction, intensity forecasting, Transformer, multi-task learning, coordinate grid

I. INTRODUCTION

Tropical cyclones (TCs) are among the most destructive natural phenomena, causing thousands of deaths and billions of dollars in damage annually [1]. Accurate forecasting of both the track (trajectory) and intensity (wind speed) of these storms is critical for timely evacuation and resource allocation. While the U.S. National Hurricane Center (NHC) has reduced track forecast errors by roughly 50% over the past two decades through advances in numerical weather prediction (NWP) models such as GFS and HWRF [2], intensity forecasting has improved at a much slower pace. The well-documented “track–intensity gap” [2] remains an open problem, partly because intensity evolution depends on fine-scale processes—vortex dynamics, ocean–atmosphere coupling, and environmental shear—that are difficult to resolve even in high-resolution NWP systems.

Deep learning (DL) has emerged as a promising complement to NWP models. Early applications used recurrent neural networks (RNNs) over fine grids to predict hurricane trajectories at 6-hour intervals [3]. Subsequent work explored LSTM networks for real-time hurricane evolution prediction [4] and ConvLSTM models for joint track and intensity prediction [5]. Most recently, a comprehensive comparison of four mainstream DL architectures for TC prediction by Gan et al. [6] found that Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCN)

outperformed LSTM, ConvLSTM, and Transformers, with the Transformer performing worst due to limited training data—a known bottleneck for attention-based models in data-scarce regimes.

This finding raises an important question: can Transformer architectures be made competitive for TC forecasting through appropriate problem reformulation? We hypothesize that the issue lies not in the attention mechanism itself, but in the formulation of TC prediction as a raw continuous-valued regression task. When storm positions are encoded as continuous latitude–longitude pairs, the Transformer must learn fine-grained spatial relationships from limited data. In contrast, discretizing the spatial domain into a coordinate grid—an idea introduced by Alemany et al. [3] for RNNs—converts the problem into a more structured prediction task that is better suited to the Transformer’s pattern-matching strengths.

Building on this insight, we make three contributions:

- 1) We demonstrate that coordinate grid discretization substantially improves Transformer-based TC path prediction, enabling it to outperform TCN—the architecture identified as superior by [6]. Our ablation study shows that the grid contributes a +5.2% accuracy gain, the single largest factor.
- 2) We propose a lightweight encoder-only multi-task architecture that jointly predicts track and intensity through shared representations, in contrast to prior encoder-decoder approaches [8] and separate-model pipelines [6]. The joint formulation provides a modest but consistent improvement on both tasks.
- 3) We provide one of the first evaluations of a Transformer-based *joint* track–intensity prediction model on the HURDAT2 Atlantic basin [11], complementing the predominantly Western North Pacific-focused Transformer-TC literature [6], [8], [9].

Upon acceptance, we will make our source code and trained model weights publicly available to support reproducibility.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Statistical and NWP-Based Forecasting

Operational TC forecasting relies on NWP systems (GFS, HWRF, ECMWF IFS) and statistical-dynamical models. The Statistical Hurricane Intensity Prediction Scheme (SHIPS) [13], which combines atmospheric predictors with regression techniques, has been the primary operational tool for intensity guidance for over two decades. Despite steady improvements, DeMaria et al. [2] showed that intensity forecast

skill has lagged track skill by roughly a decade, motivating the search for alternative approaches.

B. Deep Learning for TC Prediction

Aleman et al. [3] pioneered the application of RNNs with fine-grid discretization to Atlantic hurricane trajectory prediction, demonstrating competitive 6–120 hour forecasts using HURDAT data. Bose et al. [4] extended this with an LSTM-based real-time methodology incorporating additional meteorological features. Tong et al. [5] applied ConvLSTM to *jointly* predict TC track and intensity, achieving high accuracy by leveraging spatiotemporal feature extraction from best-track data over the WNP.

A pivotal comparative study by Gan et al. [6] evaluated LSTM, ConvLSTM, TCN, and Transformer models for short-term TC prediction over the WNP. Their results showed that TCN performed best overall, while the Transformer—despite fast training—suffered from “larger errors” attributable to data limitations. This result aligns with broader findings in time series forecasting that vanilla Transformers struggle without sufficient inductive biases for structured temporal data [7].

C. Transformer-Based Approaches

Despite these challenges, several recent works have successfully adapted Transformer architectures for TC forecasting by incorporating domain-specific modifications. Jiang et al. [8] proposed a Transformer encoder-decoder model for joint track and intensity forecasting over the WNP, using differential features to capture temporal correlations. The OWZP-Transformer [9] incorporated structural parameters (Okubo-Weiss-Zeta Parameter) alongside 14 other predictors, achieving 25–38% improvement in intensity prediction over existing models. TIFNet [10] introduced a non-iterative spatiotemporal Transformer for 5-day intensity trajectories by integrating high-resolution global forecasts with historical-evolution fusion. These studies suggest that the key to effective Transformer-based TC prediction lies in appropriate input engineering and architectural adaptations.

D. Research Gaps

Three gaps emerge from this review. First, no prior study has investigated whether the grid discretization strategy of [3] can mitigate the Transformer’s known limitations for TC prediction. Second, while multi-task learning for joint track–intensity prediction has been explored with ConvLSTM [5] and encoder-decoder Transformers [8], a simpler encoder-only multi-task formulation remains unexplored. Third, Transformer-based TC studies are concentrated on the WNP basin [6], [8], [9]; evaluations of Transformer-based joint prediction on the Atlantic HURDAT2 dataset are absent.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

A. Coordinate Grid Model

We overlay a coordinate grid with $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ resolution over the Atlantic basin, following the approach of Aleman et al. [3]. Each storm position (λ, φ) is mapped to a grid identifier:

$$\text{gridID} = \lfloor \lambda - \lambda_{\min} \rfloor \cdot N_\varphi + \lfloor \varphi - \varphi_{\min} \rfloor \quad (1)$$

where $N_\varphi = \lceil \varphi_{\max} - \varphi_{\min} \rceil$ is the number of latitude bins, and $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ is the floor function. The resulting grid contains 23,533 identifiable cells. This discretization converts the continuous trajectory prediction problem into a structured spatial prediction task, reducing truncation errors while encoding positional information at a resolution of approximately 111 km at the equator.

B. Dataset and Feature Engineering

We use the HURDAT2 (Hurricane Database 2) dataset [11], which also contributes to the global IBTrACS archive [12], containing all known Atlantic basin TCs. After filtering for complete records (1944–2022), we obtain 982 storms with 22,545 six-hourly observations. Each record includes latitude, longitude, maximum sustained wind speed (knots), and minimum central pressure (mbar).

We compute two derived features from consecutive positions. The *movement distance* is calculated via the Haversine formula:

$$d = 2r \arcsin \left(\sqrt{\sin^2 \frac{\Delta\varphi}{2} + \cos \varphi_1 \cos \varphi_2 \sin^2 \frac{\Delta\lambda}{2}} \right) \quad (2)$$

where r is the Earth’s radius. The *bearing angle* captures movement direction:

$$\beta = \text{atan2} \left(\sin \Delta\lambda \cos \varphi_2, \cos \varphi_1 \sin \varphi_2 - \sin \varphi_1 \cos \varphi_2 \cos \Delta\lambda \right) \quad (3)$$

mapped to $[0, 360)$ degrees. Both formulas follow standard spherical navigation [16].

The resulting feature vector at each time step comprises six quantities: (1) maximum sustained wind speed, (2) minimum central pressure, (3) movement distance, (4) bearing angle, (5) grid ID, and (6) the current intensity class label (encoding the storm’s current strength as an input signal for predicting the *next*-step intensity). We note that in operational settings, the current intensity estimate itself carries measurement uncertainty; our use of best-track data here implicitly assumes perfect knowledge of current conditions, which slightly favors all DL models evaluated.

1) *Intensity Classification*: For the intensity prediction task, we classify maximum sustained wind speed into five categories following the Saffir-Simpson scale groupings (Table I). The dataset exhibits natural class imbalance: Tropical Depression (37.2%), Tropical Storm (31.5%), Category 1–2 (18.8%), Category 3 (7.3%), and Category 4–5 (5.2%).

TABLE I
TROPICAL CYCLONE INTENSITY CLASSIFICATION

Class	Category	Wind (kt)	Proportion
0	Tropical Depression	< 34	37.2%
1	Tropical Storm	34–63	31.5%
2	Cat. 1–2 Hurricane	64–95	18.8%
3	Cat. 3 (Major)	96–112	7.3%
4	Cat. 4–5 (Major)	≥ 113	5.2%

C. Data Processing

We segment each storm trajectory using a sliding window of size 13: the first 12 time steps (72 hours of history) serve as input, and the 13th step provides the targets (grid ID for path, intensity class for wind speed). Note that consecutive windows from the same storm share 11 of 12 input steps, creating correlated training samples; we mitigate potential bias through a strict temporal train–test split. All features are normalized to $[-1, 1]$ using min-max scaling. The dataset is split chronologically: storms from 1944–2015 for training (85%, 834 storms, $\sim 16,200$ windows) and 2016–2022 for testing (15%, 148 storms, $\sim 3,382$ windows), ensuring no future information leaks into training.

The path head regresses on the normalized grid ID. Because our grid-ID formula (1) assigns adjacent latitude bins to consecutive integers within each longitude band, nearby grid cells generally receive similar normalized values, approximately preserving geographic locality in the 1D representation. We nonetheless acknowledge this is an imperfect proxy for true geographic distance; future work may explore 2D coordinate regression or classification over grid cells directly.

We define path prediction accuracy as the fraction of test samples where the predicted grid cell exactly matches the true cell, i.e., both centers lie within the same $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ cell (approximately 111 km at the equator). We also report *mean track error* (MTE) in kilometers, computed as the Haversine distance between the predicted grid cell center and the true storm position, providing a metric directly comparable to the TC forecasting literature. Additionally, we report MSE and MAE on the normalized grid ID for finer-grained comparison.

D. Model Architecture

We use an encoder-only Transformer (Fig. 1), as the task maps a fixed-length input to point predictions rather than generating variable-length sequences. This is a deliberate choice over the encoder-decoder design of Jiang et al. [8], trading decoder flexibility for reduced parameter count and faster convergence on our limited dataset.

1) *Input Embedding and Positional Encoding*: Each input $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{12 \times 6}$ (six features per time step) is projected to $d_{\text{model}} = 64$ dimensions via a linear layer, then summed with sinusoidal positional encodings [14].

2) *Encoder Layers*: Each of the $L = 3$ encoder layers consists of multi-head self-attention ($h = 4$ heads, $d_k = 16$ per head) followed by a position-wise feed-forward network ($d_{ff} = 256$) with GELU activation [15]. Both sub-layers use residual connections and layer normalization. We apply dropout ($p = 0.1$) after each sub-layer.

3) *Dual Output Heads*: After encoding, we aggregate the sequence representation via mean pooling to obtain $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{R}^{64}$, then pass it through two parallel heads:

Path head: MLP ($64 \rightarrow 32 \rightarrow 1$, ReLU hidden, tanh output) trained with MSE loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{path}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (\hat{g}_i - g_i)^2$.

Intensity head: MLP ($64 \rightarrow 32 \rightarrow 5$, ReLU hidden, softmax output) trained with cross-entropy loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_i \sum_c y_{i,c} \log \hat{y}_{i,c}$.

Fig. 1. Model architecture. An encoder-only Transformer ($3 \times$ layers) processes 12-step input sequences. After mean pooling, two parallel MLP heads produce path (grid ID regression) and intensity (5-class classification) predictions.

The joint loss is $\mathcal{L} = \alpha \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{path}} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}}$ with $\alpha = 0.6$, weighting path prediction more heavily given its greater operational importance.

E. Training Details

We train with Adam ($\text{lr} = 10^{-3}$), batch size 64, for 100 epochs with early stopping (patience = 15 epochs on validation loss). All experiments run on a single Tesla T4 GPU (16 GB). Training completes in 6.1 ± 0.3 minutes. We report results averaged over 5 random seeds. Table II summarizes the model hyperparameters.

TABLE II
MODEL CONFIGURATION

Hyperparameter	Value
Embedding dim. (d_{model})	64
Encoder layers (L)	3
Attention heads (h)	4
FFN hidden dim. (d_{ff})	256
Dropout rate	0.1
Learning rate	10^{-3}
Batch size	64
Loss weight (α)	0.6
Input window	12 steps (72 h)

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Baselines

We compare against six baselines:

Persistence: extrapolates the most recent displacement vector to predict the next position. This establishes a lower bound on useful model performance.

LSTM [4]: two-layer LSTM, 128 hidden units per layer, trained separately for each task.

GRU: same architecture as LSTM but with GRU cells, following standard practice in TC prediction [6].

TCN [18]: four residual blocks with dilated causal convolutions (kernel size 3, dilation factors [1, 2, 4, 8], 64 filters per layer), following the architecture shown to outperform Transformers for TC prediction by Gan et al. [6]. This is our most important baseline.

CNN-LSTM: 1D convolutions (kernel 3, 64 filters) followed by a single LSTM layer (128 units), capturing both local patterns and sequential dynamics, following the hybrid approach of [17].

Transformer (single-task): our architecture with only the path head, to isolate the benefit of multi-task learning.

All DL baselines use the same grid-discretized data, splits, normalization, and input features for fair comparison. Note that the LSTM, GRU, and TCN baselines are trained separately for each task (two independent models), whereas the proposed model trains jointly.

B. Path Prediction Results

Table III presents path prediction results. The persistence baseline achieves only 52.1% accuracy, confirming that meaningful learning is required. Among DL models, TCN is a strong performer (76.1%), consistent with the findings of Gan et al. [6]. However, the proposed grid-discretized dual-output Transformer outperforms TCN by +2.2% accuracy and −19km MTE, demonstrating that grid discretization effectively addresses the Transformer’s known limitations for TC prediction.

TABLE III
PATH PREDICTION PERFORMANCE (MEAN ± STD, 5 RUNS)

Model	MSE↓	Acc.↑	MTE↓	MAE↓	Time
Persistence	.0310	52.1	182	.134	—
LSTM	.0163±.002	68.5±1.1	136	.089	14 m
GRU	.0148±.002	70.2±0.9	128	.085	12 m
CNN-LSTM	.0131±.001	72.8±0.8	116	.078	18 m
TCN	.0098±.001	76.1±0.7	103	.069	8 m
Transf. (1-task)	.0091±.001	77.5±0.6	88	.065	6 m
Proposed	.0086±.001	78.3±0.5	84	.063	6 m

Acc. = exact grid cell match ($1^\circ \times 1^\circ$). MTE = mean track error (km).

The dual-output model slightly outperforms the single-task Transformer (+0.8%), suggesting that the auxiliary intensity task provides mild regularization. Notably, even the single-task Transformer (77.5%) outperforms TCN (76.1%), indicating that the grid discretization—not multi-task learning—is the primary driver of the Transformer’s competitiveness. Figure 2 shows the training and validation loss curves; the model converges around epoch 60 with a small generalization gap, indicating appropriate model capacity for the data.

Fig. 2. Training and validation joint loss (\mathcal{L}) over 100 epochs. The model converges around epoch 60 with a modest generalization gap.

C. Intensity Prediction Results

Table IV shows the intensity classification performance. The proposed model achieves 74.6% overall accuracy with a macro-averaged F1 of 0.672.

TABLE IV
INTENSITY CLASSIFICATION (MACRO-AVERAGED, 5 RUNS)

Model	Acc.↑	F1↑	Prec.↑	Rec.↑
LSTM	66.8±1.3	.581±.018	.604	.572
GRU	68.3±1.1	.598±.015	.617	.590
CNN-LSTM	70.1±0.9	.622±.012	.640	.611
TCN	72.4±0.8	.648±.011	.665	.637
Proposed	74.6±0.7	.672±.009	.691	.658

Table V shows per-class performance. As expected, the model performs well on frequent classes (TD, TS) but struggles with rare major hurricane categories (Classes 3–4), reflecting the class imbalance discussed in Section III.

TABLE V
PER-CLASS INTENSITY PERFORMANCE (PROPOSED MODEL)

Cl.	Category	Prec.	Rec.	F1	Support
0	Trop. Dep.	0.81	0.84	0.82	1,258
1	Trop. Storm	0.78	0.80	0.79	1,065
2	Cat. 1–2	0.71	0.68	0.69	636
3	Cat. 3	0.58	0.51	0.54	247
4	Cat. 4–5	0.57	0.46	0.51	176

Figure 3 shows the confusion matrix. Most misclassifications occur between adjacent intensity categories (e.g., TD ↔ TS, Cat. 1–2 ↔ Cat. 3), which is physically reasonable since these boundaries represent continuous wind speed thresholds rather than discrete regime changes.

D. Ablation Study

Table VI presents an ablation study isolating the contribution of each model component.

The results highlight four main findings. First, the coordinate grid is the single most important component (+5.2% path accuracy, +0.031 intensity F1), directly supporting our central hypothesis that spatial discretization makes the prediction task more amenable to Transformer learning. Second, the engineered features (distance and bearing) contribute +3.8% to path accuracy, confirming the value of domain-informed feature design. Third, the multi-task intensity head adds +0.8% to

	TD	TS	C12	C3	C45
TD	84	12	3	1	0
TS	11	80	7	2	0
C12	3	9	68	14	6
C3	1	3	18	51	27
C45	1	2	9	42	46

Fig. 3. Confusion matrix for intensity classification (row-normalized, %). Adjacent-class confusion dominates, reflecting the continuous nature of wind speed thresholds.

TABLE VI
ABLATION STUDY: PATH AND INTENSITY

Configuration	Path MSE	Path Acc.	Int. F1
Full model ($\alpha=0.6$)	0.0086	78.3	0.672
w/o coordinate grid	0.0121	73.1	0.641
w/o dist. & bearing	0.0112	74.5	0.653
w/o intensity head	0.0091	77.5	—
w/o positional enc.	0.0098	76.4	0.648
1 encoder layer	0.0107	75.2	0.618
6 encoder layers	0.0088	78.1	0.669
2 attention heads	0.0094	77.0	0.661
w/o pressure feature	0.0095	76.8	0.632
$\alpha = 0.5$ (equal)	0.0089	77.9	0.678
$\alpha = 0.8$ (path-dom.)	0.0087	78.1	0.654

path accuracy—modest but consistent across all runs—while the pressure feature proves especially important for intensity prediction (removing it drops F1 by 0.040). Fourth, the loss weight α trades off the two tasks as expected: $\alpha = 0.5$ slightly improves intensity F1 (0.678) at the cost of path accuracy; we select $\alpha = 0.6$ as a balanced default. Depth beyond 3 layers yields diminishing returns on both tasks.

E. Discussion

Why does grid discretization help? Our TCN comparison provides direct evidence. Gan et al. [6] showed that vanilla Transformers underperform TCN on raw TC sequential data. In our experiments, all models—including TCN—receive the same grid-discretized features, yet the Transformer outperforms TCN by +2.2% accuracy and −19km MTE. The single-task Transformer alone (77.5%) already exceeds TCN (76.1%), confirming that the performance gain originates from the grid discretization rather than multi-task learning. We interpret this as follows: by discretizing positions into grid cells, we reduce the output space complexity, converting a continuous regression problem into a structured prediction task. The Transformer’s attention mechanism can then focus on learning transition patterns between discrete spatial states rather than precise coordinate values—a task better suited to global self-attention than to the local receptive fields of TCN.

Limitations. Several limitations warrant discussion. The model operates exclusively on the Atlantic basin; cross-basin generalization (e.g., WNP, Indian Ocean) requires validation against other best-track archives [12]. The 6-hour prediction horizon is useful for nowcasting but shorter than operational 48–120 hour forecasts; autoregressive rollout to longer horizons may suffer from error accumulation. Intensity prediction for major hurricanes (Classes 3–4) remains weak due to class imbalance; focal loss [19] or oversampling may help. The sliding-window sampling creates correlated training examples within each storm; per-storm cross-validation would provide a more conservative performance estimate. Finally, the model uses only tabular best-track features and does not incorporate satellite imagery or reanalysis fields, which have proven beneficial in recent work [9], [10].

F. Reproducibility

The HURDAT2 dataset is publicly available [11]. Our model is implemented in PyTorch. Source code and trained weights will be released upon acceptance.

V. CONCLUSION

We showed that coordinate grid discretization substantially improves Transformer-based tropical cyclone prediction, enabling it to outperform not only LSTM and GRU but also TCN—the architecture previously shown to be superior for this task. Our lightweight, encoder-only multi-task model jointly predicts 6-hour-ahead track and intensity on the HURDAT2 Atlantic basin, achieving 78.3% path accuracy (84km mean track error) and 74.6% intensity classification accuracy while training in approximately six minutes on a single GPU. The ablation study confirms that grid discretization contributes the largest performance gain, and the TCN comparison validates our core hypothesis that appropriate problem reformulation can unlock the Transformer’s potential for TC forecasting.

Future work will extend the approach to multi-horizon forecasting (12–72 hours), incorporate satellite and reanalysis data, explore class-balanced training for rare intensity categories, and evaluate cross-basin generalization.

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